

Magnitudes and Orientations and Relation to Spin

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It is well-known that momentum is a vector and energy a number. A vector, however, may map to a scalar. Two examples include the magnitude of the vector and the dot product of the vector with a normal to a surface through which particles are passing. As a result, by using a dot product with vectors one may include them in an equation containing a related number. This equation then involves numbers or changes in numbers in time and space, but does explicitly exhibit orientations. Implicitly, however, orientations are present due to the kind of dot products which appear. As a result, one may deconstruct such number equations in order to find information about orientations. Such deconstructions, however, seem to also be more directly related to interactions because as noted p is a vector and it is this vector which creates an impulse hit. Its magnitude does not reveal enough information for an interaction if it does not collide head on with a target. Thus, the orientations are a key part of the interaction. These orientations may be expressed in terms of matrices which are then called spin matrices.

In this note, we argue that spin in quantum mechanics is related to orientation in equations described above and we consider the Klein-Gordon equation and the continuity equation of electromagnetism using the Poynting vector. Both lead to spin when one tries to deconstruct in terms of variables involved in interactions and takes into account relevant orientations. If one has equations which involve both the interaction variables and orientations directly, as in the case of Maxwell's equations, then no deconstruction of a number equation (with dot products) is needed. One may directly use these equations and combine them into one as we show. Thus, in the photon case, either the continuity equation with Poynting momentum may be deconstructed or a wave equation with spin directly created from Maxwell's equations.

Vectors Mapping to Numbers

A vector may map to a number in various manners. In physics, the modulus of a vector and its dot product with a unit vector perpendicular to a surface through which photons/particles are passing are two common examples. The importance of mapping a vector to a number is that it allows one to create equations linking the dot product of the vector with other related numbers. Two common examples involve linking E (free particle energy) and p (momentum) and linking electromagnetic energy density changes with momentum flow (Maxwell's equations for a non-source situation). Such equations involve numbers, but due to the nature of the dot products also contain embedded information about orientations. Furthermore, they seem to contain information about vectors directly related in interactions as these give physical meaning to the orientations. Otherwise, the orientations might be irrelevant. We consider two examples, namely that of the Lorentz invariant $-EE + pcpc = -mocc mocc$ (or the Klein-Gordon equation) and the energy density-Poynting momentum continuity equation with no sources.

Electromagnetism

The continuity equation involving electromagnetic energy and the Poynting vector with no sources is given by:

$$\frac{d}{dt} \text{partial} (.5 \epsilon_0 \mathbf{E} \cdot \mathbf{E} + .5/\mu_0 \mathbf{B} \cdot \mathbf{B}) + 1/\mu_0 \text{grad} \cdot (\mathbf{E} \times \mathbf{B}) = 0 \quad ((1))$$

Here $.5\epsilon_0 \mathbf{E} \cdot \mathbf{E} + .5/\mu_0 \mathbf{B} \cdot \mathbf{B}$ is energy density and $1/\mu_0 \mathbf{E} \times \mathbf{B}$ is Poynting momentum. ((1)) is a physical equation and its quantities (densities) when integrated are associated with the physical quantities of energy and momentum. One might ask: Why should one consider ((1)) any further? In other words, why would one deconstruct it? If one answers that one wishes to learn about \mathbf{E} (electric field) and \mathbf{B} (magnetic field) because they are involved in physical interactions, then one could always use the equations:

$$\frac{d}{dt} \text{partial} \mathbf{E} = \text{constant} \text{grad} \cdot \text{grad} \mathbf{E} \quad ((2a)) \text{ and}$$

$$\frac{d}{dt} \text{partial} \mathbf{B} = \text{constant} \text{grad} \cdot \text{grad} \mathbf{B} \quad ((2b))$$

The problem with ((2a)) and ((2b)) is that \mathbf{E} and \mathbf{B} are treated on the same mathematical footing. In other words, there is no orientation information provided. To see that orientation is critical for interactions, one may consider the Lorentz force:

$$\mathbf{F} = q \mathbf{E} + q \mathbf{v} \times \mathbf{B} \quad ((3))$$

As a result, in order to learn about \mathbf{E} and \mathbf{B} (vectors) which are involved linearly in force (see ((3))) one also needs orientation information. This can be provided by an equation which uses dot products with these vectors in order to create numbers, namely ((1)). In other words, the type of dot products present in ((1)) show precisely what kind of orientations are linked with physical interactions. One must, however, deconstruct the number equation ((1)) in order to see these orientations explicitly.

We have showed in a previous note (1) that ((1)) deconstructs to (setting ϵ_0 and μ_0 to 1)

$$\{ \frac{d}{dt} \text{partial} (\mathbf{E} + i\mathbf{B}) + \sigma \cdot \text{grad} (\mathbf{E} + i\mathbf{B}) \} = 0 \quad ((4a))$$

((4a)) not only shows the interaction (see ((3))) vectors, but also orientation information which is critical. Here σ is ϵ_{ijk} , i.e. the Levi-Civita symbol is the spin matrix with (i) representing the matrix label and jk , its elements. ϵ_{ijk} is a 3x3 matrix. Thus, a spin matrix appears when one tries to deconstruct an equation with numbers which includes various dot products or with various vectors. In the case of \mathbf{B} , it is not just magnitude which appears, but also the cross product which is present in ((3)) just as it is present in Maxwell's equations. Thus, orientation is key to interactions involving the \mathbf{E} (electric) and \mathbf{B} (magnetic fields). A question which may arise is: Why would one not simply deconstruct equations containing \mathbf{E} and \mathbf{B} vectors and the cross product instead of writing the cross product $\mathbf{E} \times \mathbf{B}$ in terms of a matrix: $\epsilon_{ijk} E^{(j)} B^{(k)}$? In other words, ϵ_{ijk} is a matrix (if i is its label) which creates the cross product. It seems that the matrix shows an orientation transformation more directly. A cross product also shows a kind of orientation transformation as well, but involves two vectors in general.

In particular, one might ask: Why did one not use Maxwell's equations without sources directly instead of the continuity equation which was derived from Maxwell's equations? If one considers:

$$\frac{d}{dt} \text{partial } B = \text{grad } \times E \quad \text{and} \quad \frac{d}{dt} \text{partial } E = \text{grad } \times B \quad (\text{constants set to } 1) \quad ((4b))$$

then one may see the similarity with ((4a)). Specifically ((4b)) yields:

$$\frac{d}{dt} \text{partial } (E+iB) - \text{grad } \times (E+iB) = 0 \quad ((4c))$$

((4c)) may be formally written as:

$$\frac{d}{dt} \text{partial } (E+iB) (k) + e_{jik} \text{dj } (E+iB) (k) \quad ((4d))$$

This is exactly the form of ((4a)). Thus, one does not really need to use the continuity equation with energy density and the Poynting momentum density, but obtain the result directly from Maxwell's equations, as expected. The key point, however, is that in the case of spin, one wishes to introduce a matrix in order to describe orientation operations in matrix form instead of writing ((4c)) which also contains the same orientation information.

-EE + pcpc = -mocc mocc or the Klein-Gordon Equation

The second example we consider is the Lorentz invariant $-EE + pcpc = -mocc mocc$ ((5)) or its Klein-Gordon form. Again, one uses a dot product $p \cdot p$ to map p (the momentum vector) into a number so it may appear in the same equation as E (free particle energy). Thus, its orientation is contained in this dot product, but one no longer has the linear form p (vector) which displays information about the kind of impulse hits which occur in a reaction. As a result, one starts with a number equation, the Lorentz invariant, because it contains the appropriate dot products associated with the physical orientations involved. One must then, however, linearize it in order to obtain an equation displaying the interaction variables E , p vector and m_0 (albeit in the rest frame) together with appropriate orientations. Again, these orientations are represented by matrices.

In this case, this problem was solved by Dirac in the 1920s. The linearized form is:

$$i \text{Matrix}_0 \frac{d}{dt} \text{partial } W(x,t) \text{vector} + \sigma \cdot (- \text{grad}) W(x,t) \text{vector} = mocc \text{Identity } W(x,t) \text{vector} \quad ((5))$$

$$\text{Matrix}_0 = \begin{vmatrix} I & 0 \\ 0 & I \end{vmatrix} \quad \text{where } I \text{ is the } 2 \times 2 \text{ identity}$$

$$\sigma_i = \begin{vmatrix} 0 & \text{Pauli}(i) \text{ } 2 \times 2 \text{ matrix} \\ -\text{Pauli}(i) \text{ } 2 \times 2 \text{ matrix} & 0 \end{vmatrix}$$

(see (2))

Conclusion

In conclusion, we try to investigate the idea behind equations which display spin. We argue that one often seeks an equation displaying variables which appear in an interaction directly together with their orientations which affect the interaction. It seems that such equations may be deconstructed best from equations which use dot products to map vectors (related to interactions) to numbers. This might involve a magnitude or a dot product with a vector representing a unit vector perpendicular to a surface through which photons/particles pass. It is not enough to have equations representing the interaction variables alone if their orientations are not included because these are key to the interactions. As a result, E (electric field) and B (magnetic field) satisfy the same type of wave equation, but $F = q E + q v \times B$, showing that there is a key orientation difference which must be accounted for (and is in the continuity equation including energy density and Poynting momentum density). Maxwell's equations without sources, however, display both the interaction variables E and B , but also orientations directly and so one may directly create the photon spin equation from this instead of deconstructing a continuity equation, as shown above.

Similarly, the Lorentz invariant $-E^2 + p \cdot p / c^2 = -m_0 c^2 / c^2$ contains the dot product associated with the momentum vector which leads to Dirac spin matrices when one linearizes.

References

1. Ruggeri, Francesco R. Photon Wave Equation from Continuity Equation with Poynting Vector (Part 1, Part II) (preprint, zenodo, 2021)
2. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Dirac_equation